

INGLIZ TILI ONA TILI SIFATIDA

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili ona tili sifatida ingliz tili (ENL), ingliz tili qo'shimcha til sifatida (EAL), ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida (ESL) va ingliz tili chet tili sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. (EFL) - ularning farqlari tushuntiriladi. Bu talabalarga ingliz tilini o'z ona tilidek o'rganish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ona tili, birinchi til, ona tili sifatida ingliz (ENL), qo'shimcha til sifatida ingliz (EAL), ikkinchi til sifatida ingliz (ESL) va chet tili sifatida ingliz (EFL), ikkinchi til .

АНГЛИЙСКИЙ КАК РОДНОЙ ЯЗЫК

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Аннотация: В этой статье английский как родной язык рассматривается как один из их языков: английский как родной (ENL), английский как дополнительный язык (EAL), английский как второй язык (ESL) и английский как иностранный язык. (EFL) - объясняются их различия. Это позволяет учащимся изучать английский как родной язык.

Ключевые слова: родной язык, первый язык, английский как родной язык (ENL), английский как дополнительный язык (EAL), английский как второй язык (ESL) и английский как иностранный язык (EFL), второй язык.

ENGLISH AS A MOTHER TONGUE

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Abstract: In this article, English as a native language is considered as one of their English as a Native Language (ENL), English as an Additional Language (EAL), English as a Second Language (ESL), and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) - their differences are explained. This allows students to learn English as their mother tongue.

Keywords: mother tongue, first language, English as a Native Language (ENL), English as an Additional Language (EAL), English as a Second Language (ESL), and English as a Foreign Language (EFL), second language.

A mother tongue (also native language, a first language, arterial language, or

L1) is the language or are the languages a person has learned from birth or within the critical period, or that a person speaks the best and so is often the basis for sociolinguistic identity. In some countries, the terms native language or mother tongue refer to the language of one's ethnic group rather than one's first language. Children brought up speaking more than one language can have more than one native language, and be bilingual[1]. By contrast, a second language is any language that one speaks other than one's first language.

One of the more widely accepted definitions of a native speaker is someone who was born in a particular country and was raised to speak the language of that country during the critical period of their development, The journal or qualifies as a "native speaker" of a language if they were born and immersed in the language during youth, in a family where the adults shared a similar language experience as the child. Native speakers are considered to be an authority on their given language due to their natural acquisition process regarding the language, versus having learned the language later in life. This is achieved through personal interaction with the language and speakers of the language. Native speakers will not necessarily be knowledgeable about every grammatical rule of the language, but will have good "intuition" of the rules through their experience with the language[2].

Sometimes the term mother tongue or mother language is used for the language that a person learned as a child at home (usually from their parents). Children growing up in bilingual homes can, according to this definition, have more than one mother tongue or native language.

The variety of the English language spoken by people who acquired English as their first language or mother tongue.

English as a Native Language (ENL) is commonly distinguished from English as an Additional Language (EAL), English as a Second Language (ESL), and English as a Foreign Language (EFL).

Native Englishes include American English, Australian English, British English, Canadian English, Irish English, New Zealand English, Scottish English, and Welsh English.

In recent years, the proportion of ENL speakers has steadily declined while the use of English in ESL and EFL regions has rapidly increased.

"A wide variety of countries, such as Australia, Belize, Canada, Jamaica, the United Kingdom and the United States, speak English as a native language (ENL)[3]. ENL countries are established when large numbers of English speakers migrate from other English speaking countries, displacing other languages, both local and immigrant. Other countries, such as Fiji, Ghana, India, Singapore, and Zimbabwe use English as a second language (ESL). In ESL countries the language is imported during a colonial period and promoted through education, but there is not a massive migration of native English speakers." (Roger M. Thompson, Filipino English and Taglish. John Benjamins, 2003)

ENL Varieties

"English varies markedly from one ENL territory to another, and often from one region to another within heavily populated countries such as the US and UK, a state of affairs which, as travelers know well, can lead to problems of intelligibility. In the UK, for example, there are significant differences of accent, grammar, and vocabulary between Anglophone visitors to London and many of the local people (speakers of Cockney and near-Cockney), as well as in Scotland, where many people routinely mix Scots and English. In the US, there are

significant differences between many speakers of African-American (or Black) English and what is sometimes called 'mainstream English.' . . . It is therefore risky to classify a territory as ENL and leave it at that, the ENLhood of a place being no guarantee whatever of unhampered communication in English." (Tom McArthur, *The English Languages*. Cambridge University. Press, 1998)

Standards of English

"Standard English is typically seen as 'correct' and 'grammatical,' while non-standard dialects are seen as 'wrong' and 'ungrammatical,' regardless of whether the speaker or the speaker's ancestors spoke English as a native language. Disapproval of non-standard varieties is not the prerogative of the formerly colonized. The reason that Singapore has had a Speak Good English Movement and India does not is that Singapore has a highly informal contact variety, usually known as Singlish, which has no parallel in India." (Anthea Fraser Gupta, "Standard English in the World." *English in the World: Global Rules, Global Roles*, ed. by Rani Rubdy and Mario Saraceni. Continuum, 2006)

Defining native language

- Based on origin: the language(s) one learned first (the language(s) in which one has established the first long-lasting verbal contacts).
- Based on internal identification: the language(s) one identifies with/as a speaker of;
- Based on external identification: the language(s) one is identified with/as a speaker of, by others.
- Based on competence: the language(s) one knows best.
- Based on function: the language(s) one uses most.

Defining "native speaker"

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